

ASSOCIATIONS BETWEEN CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS AND LABORATORY PARAMETERS IN ALLERGODERMATOSES

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ABSTRACT

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease with complex interactions with allergens. Although AD itself is not strictly an allergic reaction and is not necessarily associated with sensitization to allergens, patients with AD demonstrate a higher frequency of sensitization to food and inhalant allergens compared to the general population. Recent data refining the “dual-allergen exposure hypothesis” indicate that early oral exposure to allergens via an intact gastrointestinal barrier usually promotes tolerance, whereas exposure through damaged skin or respiratory barriers frequently leads to sensitization

Relevance. Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease with complex interactions with allergens. Although AD itself is not strictly an allergic reaction and is not necessarily associated with sensitization to allergens, patients with AD demonstrate a higher frequency of sensitization to food and inhalant allergens compared to the general population. Recent data refining the “dual-allergen exposure hypothesis” indicate that early oral exposure to allergens via an intact gastrointestinal barrier usually promotes tolerance, whereas exposure through damaged skin or respiratory barriers frequently leads to sensitization. Therefore, impaired skin barrier function in AD patients increases the risk of transcutaneous sensitization and may hinder oral tolerance development. Interestingly, sensitivity to contact allergens (such as metals and fragrances) is not necessarily higher in AD patients than in the general population, likely due to intrinsic properties of these allergens. Personalized allergen testing can help determine appropriate strategies for allergen avoidance and reintroduction in AD management (Zhang J. et al., 2025). Infants with AD are prone to frequent viral skin infections due to impaired epidermal barrier function and dysregulated immunity. Diagnosis and management of viral infections in AD can be challenging due to diverse clinical phenotypes and overlapping signs (Khalil N. et al., 2024). Correlation analysis of the studied parameters, accounting for age-specific paraclinical results, allowed identification of characteristic interrelationships, providing insight into the pathomechanism of virus-associated allergodermatose [1-3].

The study aimed to investigate the immunobiochemical and cytokine profiles in infants, early childhood, and preschool-aged children with virus-associated allergodermatoses. Specifically, the goals were: to determine correlations between viral antibodies (CMV, herpesvirus), total IgE, cytokines (IL-4, IL-17A, MCP-1), and mucosal immunity markers (sIgA, lysozyme) in children with allergodermatoses, to identify age-specific patterns of immune

dysregulation in virus-associated skin allergic disorders, to assess the diagnostic and prognostic value of these biomarkers in clinical practice.

Methods. A cross-sectional study was conducted including infants (0–12 months), early childhood (1–3 years), and preschool-aged children (4–5 years) with clinically confirmed virus-associated allergodermatoses, including atopic dermatitis, eczema, and urticaria. Immunological assessments included serum total IgE, IgM and IgG to cytomegalovirus (CMV) and herpesvirus (HV), and salivary secretory IgA and lysozyme. Cytokine profiling was performed for IL-4, IL-17A, and MCP-1 using ELISA methods. Correlation analysis was performed to assess relationships between viral antibodies, total IgE, cytokines, and mucosal immunity markers, stratified by age group.

Results. In infants (0–12 months), a strong negative correlation was observed between salivary sIgA and IgM to CMV ($r = -0.50$), while IgM to CMV showed a strong positive correlation with both IgM to herpesvirus ($r = 0.52$) and IgG to herpesvirus ($r = 0.53$). Additionally, IL-4 demonstrated a positive correlation with IgM to herpesvirus ($r = 0.42$), indicating concurrent allergic activation during viral infection. These infants exhibited salivary immune deficiency, with lysozyme decreasing 2.5-fold and sIgA decreasing 1.5-fold, whereas cytokine levels were markedly elevated: IL-4 increased 3.9-fold, IL-17A 215-fold, and MCP-1 6.4-fold ($p < 0.05$). In early childhood (1–3 years), IgE displayed positive correlations with IgG to CMV ($r = 0.43$), IL-4 ($r = 0.67$), and IL-17A ($r = 0.45$), whereas negative correlations were found between IgE and IgM to CMV ($r = -0.69$), IgE and IgM to herpesvirus ($r = -0.84$), IgE and MCP-1 ($r = -0.48$), and IgE and lysozyme ($r = -0.39$). Salivary immunity remained compromised, with lysozyme decreasing 2.9-fold and sIgA 3.5-fold, while cytokines were significantly elevated: IL-4 $\times 5.7$, IL-17A $\times 285$, and MCP-1 $\times 7.0$. These findings indicate that IgE serves as the most informative diagnostic marker for this age group. In preschool children (4–5 years), IgE exhibited strong correlations with viral antibodies: IgE and IgM CMV ($r = -0.98$), IgE and IgM herpesvirus ($r = -0.67$), IgE and IgG herpesvirus ($r = -1.0$), and IgE and IgG CMV ($r = 0.90$). Salivary sIgA showed a negative correlation with IgE ($r = -0.4$) and a positive correlation with IgG to herpesvirus ($r = 0.4$). Cytokine correlations revealed strong negative associations between IgE and IL-17A ($r = -0.4$) and MCP-1 ($r = -0.54$). Salivary immune deficiency persisted, with lysozyme decreasing 1.5-fold and sIgA 3-fold, while cytokine levels were significantly elevated: IL-4 $\times 4.4$, IL-17A $\times 276.5$, and MCP-1 $\times 7.3$.

Conclusion. Overall, IL-4, IL-17A, MCP-1, total IgE, and salivary sIgA are reliable diagnostic markers. The study emphasizes the importance of evaluating both systemic and mucosal immunity to guide personalized management in children with virus-associated allergodermatoses.

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